

1 **A Hybrid System Based on the Combination of Adsorption, Electrocoagulation, and**
2 **Wetland Treatment for the Effective Remediation of Industrial Wastewater from**
3 **Underground Coal Gasification (UCG)**

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5 Aleksandra Strugała-Wilczek^a, Łukasz Jałowiecki^b, Mateusz Szulc^c, Jacek Borgulat^b, Grażyna
6 Płaza^{b,d}, Krzysztof Stańczyk^a

7 ^a Central Mining Institute - National Research Institute GIG-PIB, Department of Energy Saving and Air
8 Protection, Plac Gwarków 1, 40-166 Katowice, Poland

9 ^b Institute for Ecology of Industrial Areas, Environmental Microbiology Unit, Kossutha 6, str. 40-844 Katowice,
10 Poland

11 ^c Institute of Energy and Fuel Processing Technologies (ITPE), Department of Circular Economy, Zamkowa 1,
12 41-803 Zabrze, Poland

13 ^d Silesian University of Technology, Faculty of Organization and Management, Roosevelta 26-28, 41-800
14 Zabrze, Poland

15 *correspondence author: astrugala@gig.eu

16

17 Abbreviations

18 BAT– Best Available Techniques

19 BOD – biochemical oxygen demand

20 BTEX – benzene, toluene, ethylene, xylene

21 COD – chemical oxygen demand

22 CW – constructed wetland

23 EC – electrocoagulation

24 EC50 – concentration causing 50% reduction in the bioluminescence of the bacterium
25 *Aliivibrio fischeri*

26 HRT - hydraulic retention time

27 ITPE – Institute of Energy and Fuel Processing Technologies

28 PAHs – polyaromatic hydrocarbons

29 RE – removal efficiency

30 TOC – total organic carbon

31 TU – toxicity unit

32 UCG – underground coal gasification

33 WW – wastewater

34 WWTPs - wastewater treatment plants

35 Abstract

36 The study verified the effectiveness of treating post-process underground coal gasification
37 (UCG) wastewater, containing high loads of inorganic and organic pollutants, using
38 constructed wetlands (CW) enhanced by hybrid adsorption and electrocoagulation (EC)
39 techniques. Four different system configurations were tested: wetland, EC/wetland,
40 adsorbent/wetland, and EC/adsorbent/wetland. Each experiment lasted 60 days. The feed and
41 effluents from each treatment step were analysed for their basic physicochemical parameters
42 such as metals and trace elements, phenols, sulphides, cyanides, total organic carbon (TOC),
43 chemical oxygen demand (COD), biological oxygen demand (BOD), benzene, toluene,
44 ethylene, xylene (BTEX), and polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs).

45 Systems with electrocoagulation proved to be effective in the case of metal removal. The best
46 results were obtained for Fe, Ni, Sb and As (up to 96%, 98%, 94% and 82% respectively).
47 The systems were ineffective in removing Mn. All tested systems showed the greatest
48 effectiveness in the treatment of wastewater from phenols, BTEX and CN (almost 100%
49 removal). CWs without preliminary electrocoagulation showed practically 100% effectiveness
50 in removing BTEX after 14 days of treatment. Electrocoagulation was particularly effective in
51 reduction of large quantity of PAH compounds (from 1228 $\mu\text{g/l}$ to below 0.050 $\mu\text{g/l}$).
52 Effective toxicity reduction from V class to II class after 60 days in comparison with meeting
53 the requirements contained in the Best Available Techniques (BAT) document, showed that
54 all tested systems were favorable in terms of UCG wastewater treatment. A significant
55 decrease in toxicity was observed in just 14 days (around 90% reduction of toxicity measured
56 in TU values for systems without adsorbent and around 75% for systems with adsorbent). The
57 wastewater were still toxic due to the formation of degradation intermediates of organic
58 compounds (BTEX, PAHs, phenol compounds), despite a significant decrease in the
59 concentration of contaminants, therefore toxicity assessment should be one of the evaluation
60 criteria for industrial wastewater treatment.

61

62 Keywords: adsorption, electrocoagulation, constructed wetlands, toxicity, industrial
63 wastewater treatment, underground coal gasification (UCG)

64

65 1. Introduction

66 The technology of UCG involves the in-situ conversion of coal into a valuable gas
67 product, which is suitable for chemical synthesis or can be used in electricity and heat

68 production. Although UCG is considered one of the economical and technically feasible clean
69 coal technologies, there are still some issues to be concerned about. Critical issues related to
70 environmental safety include the production of wastewater that contains a large load of
71 organic and inorganic pollutants (Camp and White, 2015; Xu et al., 2021). The characteristics
72 of UCG post-processing water are similar to coke wastewater and, as a potential source of
73 environmental pollution, require proper treatment. Process water generated during UCG may
74 originate from moisture contained in the coal bed, groundwater infiltrating from the surface,
75 water chemically bonded in minerals present in the coal seam, or water steam fed to the
76 gasifier (Grabowski et al., 2021). The formation and composition of wastewater depend on
77 the type of gasified coal and process conditions, including pressure, temperature, gasification
78 agent, reaction time, use of a scrubber, etc. (Perkins, 2018). Because wastewater from UCG
79 contains, among other substances, metals, cyanides, sulphides, phenols, polyaromatic
80 hydrocarbons (PAHs), and benzene, toluene, ethylene, xylene (as BTEX) compounds
81 (Kapusta and Stańczyk, 2011; Wang et al., 2024), cleaning such a complex matrix is a
82 challenge, both technological and financial.

83 Generally, the primary goal of wastewater treatment is to fulfil the regulatory framework
84 for water discharge with the least possible impact on the environment and human health. The
85 purification methods proposed in the literature often include adsorption and
86 electrocoagulation (Ika Pratiwi et al., 2021; Chandra Nainwal, 2024). These treatments have
87 been discussed separately across a wide range of applications; however, it is now known that
88 their limitations can be surpassed through combination with constructed wetlands (Ji et al.,
89 2022).

90 The phenomenon of adsorption on solids is well-known and commonly used on an
91 industrial scale as one of the most effective, universal, environmentally friendly, and low-cost
92 methods for blocking contaminants' mobility (Babel & Kurniawan, 2003; De Gisi et al., 2016;
93 Kamari et al., 2014; Park et al., 2016). Adsorption is suitable for different pollutants and can
94 be effectively applied over wide ranges of concentrations (Qin et al., 2020; Xiang et al., 2020;
95 Ambaye et al., 2021). A wide range of solid sorption materials have been developed and used
96 for removing solutes from solution (Gupta et al., 2009), both of natural origin (clay, natural
97 zeolites, chitosan, pumices, plant-based adsorbents) (Qin et al., 2020; Yadav et al., 2021) and
98 laboratory-synthesised (like activated charcoals or silica gels). Detailed reviews of adsorption
99 techniques involving the removal of emerging contaminants from wastewater was conducted
100 by Rathi & Kumar (2021) and Jagadeesh & Sundaram (2023). Ambaye et al. (2020) reported
101 that biochar has good adsorption capacity for typical industrial wastewater pollutants such as

102 potentially toxic metals, organic pollutants, phosphorus, and nitrogen compounds. Morin-
103 Crini et al. (2022) reviewed advanced sorption for the removal of emerging contaminants
104 (antibiotics, hormones, pesticides, surfactants, industrial products, microplastics,
105 nanomaterials, and many others), while toxic dye removal by sorption was described by Teo
106 et al. (2022) and Lan et al. (2022). Adsorption depends on the degree of surface development,
107 spatial structure, and the chemical nature of the adsorbent. For example, gasification of the
108 coal seam may increase the number of oxygen groups involved in sorption processes, and
109 consequently, the sorption capacity of the post-process UCG char may be higher than that of
110 raw coal (Strugała-Wilczek et al., 2020). The second of mentioned treatment options was
111 electrocoagulation (EC). It also is a versatile method for the simultaneous multicomponent
112 treatment of liquid effluents, which utilizes five main mechanisms: coagulation and
113 flocculation, chemical oxidation, pH adjustment, electroflotation, and microbial activity. The
114 balance between each depends on the process conditions and the type of applied electrode.
115 Iron and aluminium are mainly used when seeking the coagulation and flocculation
116 mechanism (Bani-Melhem et al., 2023; Nizam Mahmud et al., 2016); however, iron is often
117 chosen also for its effectiveness in removing heavy metals and phosphate ions. Other
118 electrode materials such as stainless steel (Nizam Mahmud et al., 2016), zinc (Gong et al.
119 2022) titanium (Trompette 2022), or graphite (Orori et al., 2010) can be used when the
120 process conditions are harsh (e.g., pH, temperature, salinity) or when chemical oxidation or
121 flotation is desired.

122 The potential for tailoring the EC process widens its applicability, and hence EC can be
123 successfully introduced in any process where the following types of contaminants need to be
124 tackled: chemical oxygen demand (COD) (Ebba Bote, 2021), heavy metals (eg. Kumar et al.
125 (2022) for Pb or Solís-Rodríguez et al. (2022) for V), organic
126 compounds/solvents/hydrocarbons (eg. Gong et al., 2017, for PAH or Abdelwahab et al.,
127 2009, for phenol index). The list is numerous and just to give the reader a reference, EC is
128 also known to be able to reduce dyes, suspended solids, emulsified oils, fertilizer compounds
129 like phosphorus and nitrogen, pesticides, and pathogens.

130 The most well studied areas of EC application are known to be linked to treatment of
131 drinking water and coagulation of industrial effluents; however, EC is known for its merits
132 also in mining (Bow et al., 2013 and 2014; Mamelkina et al., 2017), oil and gas (Kadier et al.,
133 2022), petrochemicals (Kurtoğlu-Akkaya, 2022), pharmaceuticals (Alam et al., 2021),
134 semiconductors (Lee et al., 2023), food processing (Barrera-Díaz et al, 2005), milk and dairy
135 (Ankoliya et al., 2023), agriculture and livestock (Rakhmania et al., 2022), landfilling (Sediqi

136 et al., 2021). The major advantages of electrocoagulation can thus be summarised as simple,
137 compact, highly reliable, cost-effective, efficient, optimisable for a given contaminant, and
138 generating lesser amounts of waste (sludge). Often, EC is used in conjunction with other
139 treatments, e.g., as a pretreatment before biological treatment or as a final polishing step
140 before releasing the effluent into the environment (Szul et al., 2024).

141 Constructed wetlands are artificial engineered systems simulate the natural wetlands. The
142 proven advantages of CW as green and sustainable technology have been discussed by many
143 researchers and resulted in numerous applications (Saeed and Khan, 2019; Waly et al., 2022).
144 The symbiosis between plants and rhizospheric bacteria constitutes the main factor during
145 bioremediation process in CW systems. Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR)
146 promote plant growth through secretion of various compounds such as indoleacetic acid
147 (IAA), abscisic acid (AA) and auxins. Importantly, the efficiency of wetlands in removing
148 substantial amounts of organic and inorganic contaminants has been demonstrated by many
149 authors (David et al., 2022; Lott et al., 2023; Saeed et al., 2021; Spiniello et al., 2023; Zhao et
150 al., 2021). Bioremediation by constructed wetlands is increasingly applied worldwide for the
151 removal of metals from many types of industrial effluents (Guittonny-Philippe et al., 2014).
152 However, it is important to consider the potential challenges faced by wastewater treatment
153 plants (WWTPs) located near industrial facilities, which may affect vegetation and inhibit
154 plant metabolic functions. Although particulate matter emissions, including coal dust or soot
155 emitted from coking plants, have decreased significantly in recent years, their potential impact
156 on plants in vegetated WWTPs may still be significant, especially in regions with high air
157 pollution (Roy et al., 2024).

158 The integration of physicochemical and biological technologies for the treatment of
159 effluents from various industries has been extensively discussed. =Pinedo-Hernández et al.
160 (2024) proposed an electrocoagulation-wetland system for the treatment of landfill leachate,
161 and Mella et al. (2017) researched a combination of coagulation-flocculation, adsorption, and
162 ozonation for the treatment of leather dyeing wastewater. However, there is still a limited
163 number of research publications presenting the results of using similar approaches for the
164 treatment of wastewaters generated from coal processing. In this context, Ika Pratiwi et al.
165 (2021) studied the use of electrocoagulation, adsorbents, and wetland technologies for the
166 treatment of coke oven wastewater, while Bai-Hong et al. (2023) described the efficiency of
167 coupling pulse electrocoagulation with chemical precipitation methods for the treatment of
168 greywater from coal gasification. Zhai et al. (2024) pointed out that physisorption is more

169 suitable for in situ UCG wastewater treatment than chemical coagulation. Until now, only
170 Jałowiecki et al. (2024) have tested the use of constructed wetlands for the treatment of UCG
171 wastewater.

172 To address the aforementioned research gap, the authors sought a relatively inexpensive
173 and convenient purification technology capable of efficiently treating UCG wastewater.
174 Therefore, this study proposed and tested four different system configurations: wetland,
175 electrocoagulation/wetland, adsorbent/wetland, and electrocoagulation/adsorbent/wetland.
176 The adsorbent used was char, a by-product from the same coal gasification process as the
177 contaminated water. A key strength of this study lies in the comprehensive analysis of
178 effluents from each step for their physicochemical properties, including metals and trace
179 elements, phenol index, sulphides, cyanides, total organic carbon (TOC), COD, biological
180 oxygen demand (BOD), BTEX, PAHs, and biotoxicity.

181 2. Materials and Methods

182 2.1 Wastewater and char generated from underground coal gasification process

183 The large-scale experimental simulation of underground coal gasification was conducted
184 under ambient installation pressure in a surface reactor located in „Barbara” Experimental
185 Mine, a part of GIG National Research Institute (Katowice, Poland). The bulk samples of
186 bituminous coal were obtained from the „510” seam located at a depth of 850 m in „Wesoła”
187 coal mine. The UCG process was carried out using pure oxygen as the gasification reagent.
188 During the 72 hours of the process, 292.1 kg of coal was gasified, and the initial mass of the
189 coal block was 1,365 kg. After the completion of UCG process and emptying the reactor of
190 solid residues, the representative char samples were taken for further experiments according
191 to the ISO 18283 standard (2006), crushed on a laboratory crusher to fractions below 10 mm
192 and stored at 4°C until analysis. More detailed information about the conducted experiment
193 and char can be found in Wiatowski et al. (2023).

194 The total amount of wastewater produced during the gasification experiment was 1269 kg,
195 however the real quantity of post-process wastewater obtained from coal gasification after
196 subtraction of water volume that was added to the scrubber to cool the process gases was
197 261 kg (Wiatowski et al., 2023). UCG wastewater was collected in a plastic container and
198 transported to the laboratory, where sample was filtered through a 0.45µm pore diameter
199 membrane filter under vacuum and stored at 4°C until analysis.

200 2.2 Physico-chemical analysis of liquid and solid samples

201 Optimally techniques and analytical methods were selected appropriately according to the
202 expected high concentrations of pollutants in the post-process UCG wastewater and effluents
203 from the wetland columns. All analysis were carried out in GIG-NRI in accordance with the
204 currently applicable standards. Key laboratory equipment used in analytical studies included
205 but was not limited to: ICP-OES analyser Optima 5300 DV (Perkin Elmer) for the
206 determination of metals and metalloids; Ion Chromatography System Dionex ICS-5000
207 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) for the determination of inorganic anions; HS-GC-MS analyser
208 (Agilent Technologies) for BTEX analysis; HPLC analyser 1200 series with FLD detector
209 (Agilent Technologies) for the determination of PAHs compounds.

210 The initial “Wesoła” coal sample was tested in the GIG - NRI (Katowice, Poland) and the
211 char sample was analysed at the Instituto de Ciencia y Tecnologia del Carbono (Oviedo,
212 Spain).

213 2.3 Electrocoagulation system setup

214 Continuous electrocoagulation experiments were conducted using a test rig developed at
215 the Institute of Energy and Fuel Processing Technology. The reactor consists of two chambers
216 arranged in series. While the treated liquid flows upward in each chamber, the setup allows
217 for independent control of the intensity of aeration and mixing. In the case of flotation,
218 forming froth can be continuously removed using a scraper system. A stable inflow of treated
219 liquid is maintained using a peristaltic pump, while its recovery after electrocoagulation can
220 be accomplished either by gravity or with the assistance of peristaltic pumps. The treated
221 wastewater is directed into the receiving tank from which effluent sampling is performed.

222 Two laboratory power supplies can be utilized in this system: the Twintex TP-2305 (30V DC,
223 2x5A) or the Elektro-Automatik GmbH & Co. KG PS8080-60 T (80V DC, 60A). The choice
224 depends on the expected current demand and the operating mode of the reactor (single-stage
225 or two-stage). Two illustrative photos of the setup are presented in Fig. 1 while Fig. 2 depicts
226 a schematic diagram of the electrocoagulation reactor used here to pretreat UCG wastewater
227 before phytoremediation. In Fig. 1 (B) the flow is from the bottom left side of the left
228 chamber upwards to the overflow, and similarly for the subsequent second (right) EC
229 chamber.

230
231

(a) (b)

232 Fig. 1. Test stand for testing continuous electrocoagulation processes: (a) a close-up of both reactor
233 chambers, agitators, scrapers, electrodes, power supply and agitators; (b) a general view of the
234 reactor, supply and receiving tanks and pumps.

235

236 Fig. 2. Diagram of the EC reactor system used to pre-treat the UCG wastewater before its
237 phytoremediation.

238 The UCG wastewater was treated using a single-stage, constant-current mode. The
239 wastewater was introduced into the reactor from an inlet located at the bottom of the reactor's
240 side wall (left side in the figures), and the flow was kept constant at $20 \text{ dm}^3/\text{h}$. EC was carried
241 out using a single pair of horizontally aligned electrodes, both having equal total surface areas
242 of 788 cm^2 . Both electrodes consisted of four flat Fe (Armco) plates connected by rods. The
243 iron steel used in this research was $>99.5\%$ Fe grade 04 J according to PN 89/H-84023/02
244 standard, having $C_{\text{max}}=0.035\%$, $Mn_{\text{max}}=0.25\%$, $Si_{\text{max}}=0.02\%$, $P_{\text{max}}=0.025\%$, $S_{\text{max}}=0.030\%$,
245 $Cr_{\text{max}}=0.10\%$, $Ni_{\text{max}}=0.10\%$, $Cu_{\text{max}}=0.10\%$, $Al_{\text{max}}=0.02\%-0.07\%$. The anode and cathode were
246 separated by 25 mm , while the power was supplied via electrical connectors located in the
247 sidewalls of the reactor.

248 In this arrangement, it was found that the location of the cathode plays a role in removing
249 the sludge that forms on the surface of the anode and causes resistance to the flow of current,
250 affecting the structure of the flocs produced (floating flocks or sedimenting precipitate). Thus,
251 during this series of experiments, the cathode was located below the anode, Moreover, a radial
252 mixer was used to ensure good mixing of the feedstock entering the reactor and to guarantee
253 turbulent flow through the electrode zone.

254 During the experiments, the temperature of the effluent ranged from 15 to 18°C. The
255 constant flow of current was regulated and maintained by the power supply. The 4.6 A current
256 allowed here to feed into the wastewater the dose of Fe equal to 204 mg/dm³.

257 The basic physicochemical characteristics of raw UCG wastewater and UCG wastewater
258 after the EC treatment were evaluated by the Laboratory of Analytical Chemistry at the
259 Institute of Energy and Fuel Processing Technology (Zabrze, Poland).

260 2.3.1 Introducing sulphides and cyanides into the wastewater before the electrocoagulation 261 treatment

262 Cyanides and sulphides are known to be notoriously difficult contaminants to measure due
263 to their reactive characteristic. Hence their concentrations in solutions and speciation tend to
264 change over time.

265 Based on experience, wastewaters produced during gasification of hard coals can contain
266 well over 15 mg/dm³ of cyanides and 40 mg/dm³ of sulphides. However, due to the time gap
267 between the UCG gasification experiment and the phytoremediation studies, the samples of
268 raw UCG wastewater intended to be treated using EC contained only traces of these
269 contaminants. Specifically, the sulphides concentration did not exceed the lower detection
270 limit herein used UV-VIS method (<0.1 mg/dm³), while the cyanide concentration was
271 measured to be equal to 1 mg/dm³. Therefore, it was decided to artificially introduce the
272 above-mentioned concentrations of cyanides and sulphides into the UCG wastewater before
273 treating the effluent in EC reactor.

274 The pH of the UCG wastewater was in the range of 8-9. hence sulphides mainly exist in
275 the solution in the form of undissociated, soluble H₂S (gas) and HS⁻. During
276 electrocoagulation, the pH increases, leading to an increase in the amount of available free
277 sulphide ions. To limit the emission of gaseous hydrogen sulphide and avoid the need to
278 artificially increase the pH of the UCG wastewater prior to its EC, sulphides were added to
279 the solution just before the EC experiments. Cyanides are known to form complexes over time

280 and react with heavy metals, but they can also undergo oxidation with hydrocarbons available
281 in the solution. Compared to sulphides though, their nature is much less volatile.

282 The aforementioned concentrations of 15 and 40 mg/dm³ of cyanide and sulphide ions,
283 respectively, were achieved by adding potassium cyanide (KCN, manufactured by Thermo
284 Scientific) and hydrated sodium sulphide (Na₂S, manufactured by Warchem Sp. z o.o.) to the
285 solution.

286 2.4 Wetland columns setup

287 Four experimental vertical flow constructed wetlands (VFCWs) were established, each
288 containing 12 seedlings of common reed (*Phragmites australis*). The 0.3 m diameter columns
289 were filled with layers of compost (0.01 m), sand (0.02 m) and gravel (0.03 m). Two columns
290 contained an additional 0.05 m thick layer of UCG coal sandwiched between the sand layers,
291 while the volume of the remaining layers was reduced accordingly. The wastewater was
292 diverted through each column into 100-liter tanks. After a month of stabilization with tap
293 water, the wastewater was discharged. The hydraulic retention time (HRT) in each column
294 was maintained at 2 days. Four experimental systems combined physicochemical and
295 biological treatment: (1) VFCW with recirculation of raw wastewater, (2) VFCW with
296 recirculation of wastewater after the electrocoagulation process, (3) VFCW with UCG char
297 and recirculation of raw wastewater, and (4) VFCW with UCG char and recirculation of
298 wastewater after electrocoagulation (Fig. 3). Physicochemical analyses of the recirculated
299 water have started two weeks after wastewater discharge.

300
 301 Fig. 3. Diagram of the experimental systems setup – Vertical Flow Constructed Wetlands
 302 (VFCW).

303 2.5 Toxicity assessment

304 Toxicity analysis of UCG wastewater, UCG wastewater after electrocoagulation and effluents
 305 from the wetland columns were carried out in accordance with the Microtox assay system
 306 (MAS) according to the standard ASTM Standard Method (D5660) entitled “Standard Test
 307 Method for Assessing the Microbial Detoxification of Chemically Contaminated Water and
 308 Soil Using a Toxicity Test with a Luminescent Marine Bacterium”. The assay measures the
 309 luminescence of the bioluminescent marine bacterium *Aliivibrio fischeri* (ATCC 49387). The
 310 measures were done using the Microtox M500 toxicity analyser (ISO Standard 11348-3:2007)
 311 serving both as an incubator and a photometer. The analyses were done in two stages.
 312 Initially, the basic test on non-diluted samples was carried out following the standard
 313 procedures of the manufacturer. Next, toxicity was assessed on sample solutions diluted with
 314 2% NaCl to achieve more than a 50% effect over the initial screening. The luminescence
 315 inhibition after 15 min was taken as the endpoint. The 15 min Microtox™ test is slightly more
 316 sensitive than the 5 min. test (Sönmez and Sivri, 2020). The EC50 values (concentration
 317 causing 50% reduction in the bioluminescence of the bacteria) and the corresponding 95%
 318 confidence intervals were computed using the MicrotoxOmni® Software. The lower the
 319 EC50 value, the greater the toxicity of the sample. The toxicity unit (TU) was calculated in
 320 accordance with the following equation:

321
$$TU = (1/EC50) \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

322 Finally, obtained results were ranked based on TU values into one of five classes described by
 323 Persoone et al. (2003). Table 1 presents the toxicity classification based on TU values.

324 Table 1. Toxicity classification based on TU values.

Toxicity classes	Toxicity Unit (TU)	Toxicity assessment
Class I	0	Non-toxic
Class II	<1	Slightly toxic
Class III	1 - 10	Toxic
Class IV	10 - 100	Highly toxic
Class V	>100	Extremely toxic

325 To evaluate the results the toxicity criteria based on the EC50 value proposed by Vasseur et
 326 al. (1986) was also used. The following toxicity criteria are as follows:

- 327 - $EC50 > 100\%$ – non-toxic samples
- 328 - $10\% < EC50 < 100\%$ – slightly toxic samples
- 329 - $1\% \leq EC50 \leq 10\%$ – toxic samples
- 330 - $EC50 < 1\%$ – highly toxic samples

331 Each sample was run in triplicates assay. Toxicity test was evaluated in the microbiological
 332 laboratory of the Institute for Ecology of Industrial Areas (Katowice, Poland).

333 3 Results and discussion

334 3.1 Raw coal and post-process UCG char characteristics

335 The results of proximate and ultimate analysis of gasified coal and post-process UCG char are
 336 presented in Table 2. The elemental analysis of the UCG char is presented in Table 3.

337 Table 2. Analysis of coal and UCG post-process char (Wiatowski et al., 2023).

Parameter	Sample	
	Coal	Post-process UCG char
<i>Analytical state</i>		
Moisture W (%)	3.49	0.80
Ash A (%)	2.15	6.24
Volatile matter content V_r (%)	30.12	-
Total sulphur S_t (%)	0.21	0.21
Calorific value Q^f (kJ/kg)	31,458	-
Carbon C (%)	82.01	90.81
Hydrogen H (%)	5.18	0.77
Nitrogen N (%)	2.24	1.42

338 Table 3. Elements content in the mineral matter of char derived from UCG of “Wesoła” coal
 339 (Wiatowski et al., 2023).

Parameter	Post-process UCG char
Fe (%)	11.2
Mn (%)	0.2
As (ppm)	11.9
Cr (ppm)	450
Zn (ppm)	494
Cu (ppm)	562
Pb (ppm)	102
Ti (%)	0.3

340 Due to the high carbon content and relatively small number of heteroatoms (Table 2), the
 341 gasified “Wesoła” coal is poorly reactive. It is worth paying attention to the relatively high
 342 content of Cr, Zn, Cu and Pb in obtained UCG char (Table 3). Despite the UCG process being
 343 carried out in a reactive atmosphere of pure oxygen, the resulting char is characterized by
 344 small specific surface area S_{BET} ($9 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), whereas the total pore volume V_T was $0.005 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$,
 345 and the N_2 micropore volume was $0.004 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$. The textural parameters of the adsorbent were
 346 determined based on the nitrogen adsorption isotherm at a temperature of 77.3 K (Wiatowski
 347 et al., 2023).

348 3.2 Electrocoagulation pretreatment

349 After treating the raw UCG wastewater with EC, the percentage removal efficiency η_i was
 350 calculated using the following formula:

$$\eta_i = \left(1 - \frac{C_{i\text{outlet}}}{C_{i\text{inlet}}} \right) \times 100 (\%) \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

351 where:

352 $C_{i\text{inlet}}$ – concentration of component i at the inlet to the reactor (mg/dm^3),

353 $C_{i\text{outlet}}$ – concentration of component i at the outlet from the reactor (mg/dm^3).

354 Some of the parameters and components tested in this work were noticed to have higher value
 355 at the outlet (treated effluent) than measured for the inlet (effluent fed). In such case the value
 356 of η_i has negative value, representing gain instead of removal.

357 As indicated before, laboratory analyses were performed on the day of the experiment and
 358 immediately after electrocoagulation pretreatment at ITPE. The concentration of BTEX and
 359 PAHs was determined in the GIG-NRI laboratories. Table 4 presents all process and
 360 efficiency data measured during EC of the UCG wastewater.

361 Table 4. Collation of the EC process and efficiency parameters for pretreatment of UCG wastewater.

Stream	Feed*	Treated*	Removal efficiency (%)
pH (-)	8.65	8.98	-
Conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)	2000	1860	-
Redox (mV)	-135	-153	-
Free cyanide (mg/dm^3)	14.60	0.72	95.06
Sulphide (mg/dm^3)	39.20	6.18	84.24
COD (mg/dm^3)	355.70	243.2	31.63
Phenol index (mg/dm^3)	23.10	19.4	16.02
Al (mg/dm^3)	2.52	<0.125	>95.04
Fe (mg/dm^3)	0.179	2.67	-1391
Mn (mg/dm^3)	0.333	<0.02	>93.99
Ni (mg/dm^3)	0.492	0.586	-19.11
Sb (mg/dm^3)	0.080	0.07	12.5
Zn (mg/dm^3)	0.213	<0.02	>90.61
Sum of metals (mg/dm^3)	3.817	3.491	8.54
Naphthalene (mg/dm^3)	0.294	<0.000050	>99.98
Acenaphthene (mg/dm^3)	0.0105	<0.000050	>99.52
Fluorene (mg/dm^3)	0.036	<0.000050	>99.86
Phenanthrene (mg/dm^3)	0.142	<0.000050	>99.96
Anthracene (mg/dm^3)	0.042	<0.000050	>99.88
Fluoranthene (mg/dm^3)	0.135	<0.000050	>99.96
Pyrene (mg/dm^3)	0.155	<0.000050	>99.97
Benzo(a)anthracene (mg/dm^3)	0.054	<0.000050	>99.91
Chrysene (mg/dm^3)	0.154	<0.000050	>99.97
Benzo(b)fluoranthene (mg/dm^3)	0.039	<0.000050	>99.87
Benzo(k)fluoranthene (mg/dm^3)	0.024	<0.000050	>99.80
Benzo(a)pyrene (mg/dm^3)	0.036	<0.000050	>99.86
Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene (mg/dm^3)	0.018	<0.000050	>99.72
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene (mg/dm^3)	0.052	<0.000050	>99.90
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene (mg/dm^3)	0.035	<0.000050	>99.86
Sum of PAHs (mg/dm^3)	1.228	<0.000050	>99.99(6)
Benzene (mg/dm^3)	2.464	0.263	89.33
Toluene (mg/dm^3)	0.802	0.048	94.01
Ethylbenzene (mg/dm^3)	0.042	0.00012	99.71
m,p-xylene (mg/dm^3)	0.153	0.0033	97.84
o-xylene (mg/dm^3)	0.139	0.0042	96.98
Sum of BTEX (mg/dm^3)	3.599	0.320	91.11

362 * mean value

363 The electrocoagulation pretreatment resulted in CN^- , S^{2-} , and COD removal efficiencies of
 364 95%, 84%, and 32%, respectively. A minor decline was also observed in the phenol index;
 365 however, the change was minimal (16%). Additionally, a beneficial effect was noted on the

366 removal of most trace metals. The primary contaminating metal remaining in the solution was
367 attributed to the excess of iron, while a slight increase in the concentration of Ni was also
368 observed. Interestingly, EC also facilitated the removal of BTEX from the effluent of the
369 UCG process. Consequently, it was determined that the continuous EC system applied here
370 allowed for the reduction of BTEX to a level of 0.32 mg/dm^3 , resulting in a 91% reduction.
371 The highest effectiveness of removal was recorded in the case of removing PAHs compounds
372 ($>99.996\%$), which is consistent with the research conducted by Gong et al. (2017) who found
373 that EC treatment effectively removed a total of 86% of PAHs by mass in the effluent after
374 30 min. treatment of industrial wastewater.

375 3.3 Treatment of the UCG effluents in CW setup

376 The raw UCG wastewater was biologically treated with a set consisting of four constructed
377 wetland columns, and in the case of two columns, water was introduced into the system after
378 the initial electrocoagulation procedure. The effluents from the constructed wetlands were
379 collected and analysed after 14 and 45 days of treatment. The toxicity analysis of effluents
380 was performed after 14, 30, 45 and 60 days. UCG wastewater treatment experiments were
381 carried out in four different systems: CW1 (wetland), CW2 (electrocoagulation/wetland),
382 CW3 (UCG char/wetland), CW4 (electrocoagulation/char adsorbent/wetland). Raw post UCG
383 process wastewater was fed to the CW1 and CW3 systems, while wastewater after initial
384 pretreatment by EC was fed to the CW2 and CW4 systems. The composition of raw water
385 and water after electrocoagulation, as well as leachates collected after 14 and 45 days from
386 wetland columns CW1/CW3 and CW2/CW4 are presented in Tables 5 and 6.

387 As in the case of electrocoagulation, also here the removal efficiency η_i was calculated
388 according to Equation 2. The percent removal efficiency after 14 and 45 days of treatment for
389 metals and metalloids, inorganic contaminants and organic contaminants is presented in
390 Figure 4a, 4b and 4c, respectively. The exact calculated values are available in the supplement
391 in Table A.1 and Table A.2.

392 Due to the lack of legal regulations regarding the composition of post-process UCG
393 wastewater and the similarity of its matrix to wastewater from the coke industry, the obtained
394 values of individual pollutants were compared to the Best Available Techniques (BAT)
395 conclusions document (2012). The maximum concentrations of pollutants in treated coking
396 wastewater recommended in BAT are: COD $<220 \text{ mg/dm}^3$; BOD $<20 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, free sulphides
397 $<0.1 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, thiocyanides $<4 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, free cyanides $<0,1 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, PAHs $<0.05 \text{ mg/dm}^3$,
398 phenol index $<0.5 \text{ mg/dm}^3$, and total nitrogen $<15\text{-}50 \text{ mg/dm}^3$. Concentrations obtained in the

399 experiments that exceed the BAT levels are marked in bold in Tables 5 and 6. In relation to
400 these regulations, all tested systems successfully treated the wastewater (WW). The only
401 instances where limits were exceeded after 45 days of treatment involved the COD and BOD
402 values, specifically observed in the constructed wetland (CW1). Small discrepancies in the
403 characteristics of wastewater after the EC process can be noticed between Tables 4 and 6.
404 These discrepancies arise from the fact that the analyses were conducted at separate times,
405 and during storage, the samples were only refrigerated and not otherwise stabilised.
406 Nevertheless, these differences do not affect the interpretation of the observations discussed
407 later.

408 Table 5. Physicochemical composition of raw UCG post-process wastewater and changes in composition after CW1 and CW3 treatment. (CW1 – wetland,
 409 CW3 - UCG char/wetland).

Parameter	Unit	Raw WW		CW1		CW3	
		day 0	day 14	day 45	day 14	day 45	
pH	-	8.4	7.8	7.2	7.8	7.7	
Conductivity	µS/cm	1910	1260	919	1540	1430	
Redox	mV	176	225	212	232	237	
Ammonia	mg/dm ³	170	55	15	24	1.2	
Total nitrogen	mg/dm ³	150*	82*	23	80*	15	
Nitrate	mg/dm ³	0.60	1.9	10	170	40	
Nitrite	mg/dm ³	<0.006	2.6	0.31	23	0.90	
Chloride	mg/dm ³	279	228	240	275	284	
Sulphate	mg/dm ³	54.7	45	29	123	116	
Total cyanide	mg CN/dm ³	2.3	0.020	0.013	0.037	0.0040	
Sulphide	mg/dm ³	0.022	0.023	<0.02	<0.02	<0.02	
Total phosphorus	mg P/dm ³	<0.065	3.36	0.50	0.18	0.18	
BOD	mg O ₂ /dm ³	120*	120*	22*	47*	3.8	
COD	mg O ₂ /dm ³	303*	217	240*	98	105	
TOC	mg C/dm ³	80	86	90	37	45	
Phenol index	mg/dm ³	15*	<0.001	0.002	0.010	<0.001	
Fe	mg/dm ³	0.015	4.11	2.30	0.17	0.053	
Mn	mg/dm ³	0.36	0.48	0.43	0.18	0.21	
Sb	mg/dm ³	0.090	0.014	0.005	0.033	0.020	
As	mg/dm ³	<0.05	0.027	0.0097	0.011	0.012	
B	mg/dm ³	0.30	0.32	0.29	0.45	0.41	
Cr	mg/dm ³	<0.005	0.0027	0.0020	0.0011	<0.0005	
Zn	mg/dm ³	0.24	0.11	0.020	0.12	0.014	
Al	mg/dm ³	0.18	0.20	0.14	0.012	0.032	
Cd	mg/dm ³	<0.001	<0.0005	<0.0005	0.0005	<0.0005	

Co	mg/dm ³	<0.005	0.016	0.0080	0.0062	0.0059
Cu	mg/dm ³	<0.01	0.0072	0.0043	0.010	0.0073
Mo	mg/dm ³	0.0051	<0.005	<0.005	0.0078	0.012
Ni	mg/dm ³	0.54	0.073	0.020	0.071	0.013
Pb	mg/dm ³	<0.02	0.017	<0.005	0.0072	<0.005
Hg	mg/dm ³	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Se	mg/dm ³	<0.05	<0.005	<0.005	0.011	<0.005
Ti	mg/dm ³	<0.005	0.013	0.0072	0.0017	0.0014
Naphthalene	ug/dm ³	294	0.12	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Acenaphthene	ug/dm ³	10.5	<0.050	<0.050	0.093	<0.050
Fluorene	ug/dm ³	36	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Phenanthrene	ug/dm ³	142	<0.050	0.087	<0.050	<0.050
Anthracene	ug/dm ³	42	0.08	<0.050	0.10	<0.050
Fluoranthene	ug/dm ³	135	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Pyrene	ug/dm ³	155	0.10	0.091	0.12	<0.050
Benzo(a)anthracene	ug/dm ³	54	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Chrysene	ug/dm ³	154	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	ug/dm ³	39	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	ug/dm ³	24.5	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Benzo(a)pyrene	ug/dm ³	36	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene	ug/dm ³	18	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	ug/dm ³	52	<0.050	0.059	<0.050	<0.050
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	ug/dm ³	35	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
PAHs (15 compounds)	ug/dm ³	1228*	0.30	0.24	0.31	<0.050
Benzene	ug/dm ³	2464	<0.020	0.21	0.49	0.21
Toluene	ug/dm ³	802	0.51	<0.020	2.01	<0.020
Ethylbenzene	ug/dm ³	42	0.15	0.20	0.24	<0.020
m,p-xylene	ug/dm ³	153	0.42	2.82	0.65	<0.040
o-xylene	ug/dm ³	139	0.13	1.01	0.44	<0.020

BTEX (incl. styrene) ug/dm³ 3599 1.21 4.2 3.8 0.21

410 *concentrations exceeding the recommended values from the BAT document (2012)

411

412 Table 6. Physicochemical composition of UCG post-process wastewater (WW) after electrocoagulation (EC) and changes in composition after CW2 and CW4
413 treatment (CW2 - electrocoagulation/wetland, CW4 - electrocoagulation/UCG char/wetland).

Parameter	Unit	WW after EC		CW2		CW4	
		day 0	day 14	day 45	day 14	day 45	
pH	-	9.1	7.8	7.4	8.2	7.6	
Conductivity	μS/cm	1670	1490	1610	1720	1760	
Redox	mV	100	221	204	197	202	
Ammonia	mg/dm ³	190	43	0.40	56	1.0	
Total nitrogen	mg/dm ³	170*	75*	34	80*	5.5	
Nitrate	mg/dm ³	<0.5	21	120	6.0	1.2	
Nitrite	mg/dm ³	<0.006	32	0.53	2.6	0.12	
Chloride	mg/dm ³	298	273	310	277	372	
Sulphate	mg/dm ³	85.0	187	222	184	240	
Total cyanide	mg CN/dm ³	8.1*	0.072	0.41	0.30	0.44	
Sulphide	mg/dm ³	0.14*	<0.02	<0.02	<0.02	<0.02	
Total phosphorus	mg P/dm ³	<0.07	0.33	0.19	0.082	0.38	
BOD	mg O ₂ /dm ³	110*	35*	2.3	82*	8	
COD	mg O ₂ /dm ³	237*	72	49	140	165	
TOC	mg C/dm ³	65	24	25	50	67	
Phenol index	mg/dm ³	16*	0.018	0.0013	0.0010	0.0021	
Fe	mg/dm ³	3.79	0.16	0.22	0.34	0.70	
Mn	mg/dm ³	<0.005	0.024	0.11	0.12	0.44	
Sb	mg/dm ³	<0.05	0.0068	<0.005	0.014	<0.005	
As	mg/dm ³	<0.05	0.0065	0.0091	0.015	0.017	
B	mg/dm ³	0.46	0.29	0.29	0.43	0.3	

Cr	mg/dm ³	<0.005	0.0005	<0.0005	0.0009	0.0013
Zn	mg/dm ³	<0.05	0.088	0.018	0.023	0.032
Al	mg/dm ³	<0.1	<0.01	0.031	0.027	0.047
Cd	mg/dm ³	<0.001	<0.0005	<0.0005	<0.0005	<0.0005
Co	mg/dm ³	0.015	0.011	0.014	0.0099	0.0086
Cu	mg/dm ³	<0.01	0.0090	0.0065	0.016	0.0057
Mo	mg/dm ³	0.010	0.0083	0.0081	0.0096	0.0087
Ni	mg/dm ³	0.67	0.083	0.051	0.060	0.016
Pb	mg/dm ³	<0.02	<0.005	<0.005	<0.005	<0.005
Hg	mg/dm ³	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Se	mg/dm ³	<0.05	<0.005	<0.005	0.0076	<0.005
Ti	mg/dm ³	<0.005	0.0009	0.0013	0.0018	0.0033
Naphthalene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Acenaphthene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Fluorene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Phenanthrene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	0.057	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Anthracene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	0.12	0.98	0.080	<0.050
Fluoranthene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Pyrene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	0.10	<0.050	0.053	0.11
Benzo(a)anthracene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Chrysene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Benzo(b)fluoranthene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Benzo(k)fluoranthene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Benzo(a)pyrene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Dibenzo(a,h)anthracene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050
Indeno(1,2,3-cd)pyrene	ug/dm ³	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	<0.050	0.16
PAHs (15 compounds)	ug/dm ³	<0.050	0.27	0.98	0.13	0.27
Benzene	ug/dm ³	263	0.16	<0.020	0.76	<0.020

Toluene	ug/dm ³	48	0.73	<0.020	0.66	<0.020
Ethylbenzene	ug/dm ³	1.2	0.19	<0.020	0.19	<0.020
m,p-xylene	ug/dm ³	3.3	0.50	<0.040	0.61	1.80
o-xylene	ug/dm ³	4.2	0.17	<0.020	0.31	0.50
BTEX (incl. styrene)	ug/dm ³	320	1.75	<0.040	2.53	2.30

414 *concentrations exceeding the recommended values from the BAT document (2012)

415
416

(a)

417
418

(b)

419
420 (c)

421 Figure 4. Removal efficiency in tested systems: (a) metal and metalloids; (b) inorganic contaminants;
422 (c) organic contaminants (CW1 – wetland, CW2 - electrocoagulation/wetland, CW3 - char/wetland ,
423 CW4 - electrocoagulation/char/wetland; the lower y-axis scale has been limited to 100% to maintain
424 the readability of the chart).

425 WW after electrocoagulation was characterized by higher concentrations of NH_4 , total
426 nitrogen, chlorides and sulphates, Fe, B, Co, Mo, Ni (Table 6). Phenol index was rather
427 constant compared to raw wastewater (Table 5).

428 Regarding metals and metalloids, better removal efficiency was observed in the
429 electrocoagulated systems CW2 and CW4 (Figure 4a). The exception was Mn, which
430 appeared in the CW2 and CW4 effluents, and its concentration increased with the time of the
431 experiment (Table 6). It is worth noting that Mn is released in both the CW system and the
432 CW-adsorbent hybrid system, and only the introduction of EC achieved net removal of this
433 contaminant. Cd, Pb and Hg were not detected in raw water and purified leachates, which is
434 advantageous from the environmental point of view, because these elements belong to heavy
435 metals with highly toxic properties. An increase in concentration was observed in the case of
436 Cu (CW4) and Zn (CW2) after 14 days of the experiment, but it occurred at a trace level
437 (Table 6). The best effects of wastewater treatment after electrocoagulation were observed for
438 Fe, Ni, Sb, As, and the weakest for B, Mo, and Co (Figure 4a). B remains at a very low level
439 and none of the tested methods demonstrated its effective and reproducible removal. It is
440 worth noting that the longer experiment time did not have a positive effect for all elements - a

441 decrease in removal efficiency after 45 days occurred in the case of Fe, As, Cr (CW4), Zn, Al,
442 Co (CW2) and Ti (Figure 4a).

443 Better removal efficiency was observed in the system after electrocoagulation, which did not
444 contain post-process char (CW2), what may indicate either the potential leaching of metals
445 from this fine-grained material, or better wetland efficiency, which compared to CW4 due to
446 the lack of an additional adsorbent layer occupied a larger active area.

447 It is worth noting, however, that raw water without preliminary electrocoagulation was
448 purified of metals more effectively in the presence of adsorbent (CW3). Interestingly, the
449 degree of purification increased with the time of the experiment, contrary to what happened in
450 the system with a sorbent and after electrocoagulation, CW4 (e.g. for Ti, Zn, Cr). Systems
451 without a preliminary electrocoagulation process did not remove Fe as effectively, while Mn
452 was removed to a relatively small extent only in the system with the CW3 adsorbent (the
453 fractional removal of Mn was at the level of 50% and 41.7% after 14 and 45 days,
454 respectively). The constructed wetland itself (CW1 system) relatively effectively removes
455 most metals except Fe, Mn, B, Co, and Ti.

456 It seems that columns CW1 and CW3 better remove phenolic compounds from wastewater
457 (Table 5), while the phenol index in leachates from columns CW2 and CW4 remained at a
458 trace level (Table 6). Total nitrogen was best removed by the CW4 column, and the worst by
459 the CW2 column, but these differences were not significant. CW2 and CW4 columns, i.e.
460 systems in which electrocoagulation was used, were more effective in removing sulphides
461 (Figure 4b). In the case of nitrates, a significant increase in concentration after 14 days and
462 then a decrease on day 45 was observed in the presence of the sorbent (column CW3). An
463 initial increase and then a decrease in concentration was observed for each of the tested
464 systems except the CW2 column (electrocoagulation/wetland). In the CW2 column, a
465 significant increase in the concentration of nitrates in the leachate was recorded over time
466 (Table 6), which indicates the occurrence of conditions unfavourable to denitrification
467 processes.

468 Although electrocoagulation turned out to be particularly effective in the removal of PAH
469 compounds (from 1228 $\mu\text{g/l}$ to below 0.050 $\mu\text{g/l}$), trace amounts of these compounds
470 appeared in the leachates obtained after the CW2 and CW4 column (Table 6), and their
471 content increased with over the duration of the experiment. Interestingly, raw water without
472 electrocoagulation introduced to the CW1 and CW3 columns was purified by almost 100%,
473 and the PAHs content decreased with the duration of the experiment, even to a level below the

474 detection limit of $<0.050 \mu\text{g/l}$ after 45 days in the case of the CW3 column (Table 5). In the
 475 electrocoagulation process, 91.1% of compounds from the BTEX group were removed (Table
 476 4), and then wastewater was further cleaned on CW2 and CW4 columns to the level of 99.3%
 477 and 100%, respectively (Table 6). A similar or even better effect was achieved in the CW1
 478 and CW3 systems, which after 14 days showed practically 100% effectiveness in removing
 479 BTEX without preliminary coagulation (Table 5). The use of a preliminary coagulation
 480 procedure to purify wastewater from PAH and BTEX compounds does not generate
 481 additional benefits (Fig. 4c). The use of a fine-grained adsorbent in the form of post-process
 482 char does not affect the change in the concentration of these compounds in wastewater,
 483 although, according to Zhao (2021), sediments have a strong affinity for hydrophobic organic
 484 pollutants and therefore can be responsible for PAHs mechanism removal in CW.
 485 Total organic carbon (TOC) reflects the total organic matter content in wastewater and can be
 486 a comprehensive indicator of organic pollution. Changes in the content of organic
 487 contaminants are shown in Figure 5a. As can be seen, the most effective and lasting TOC
 488 decrease was recorded in the case of the CW2 system, i.e. electrocoagulation integrated with
 489 constructed wetlands. In turn, the addition of an adsorbent causes an initial decrease, but then
 490 an increase in the organic matter content in the sample.

491
 492 (a)

493
494 (b)

495 Figure 5. Changes in organic pollutant indicators: (a) TOC; (b) COD/BOD ratio in wastewater
496 samples treated in four different CW systems (CW1 – wetland, CW2 - electrocoagulation/wetland,
497 CW3 - char/wetland , CW4 - electrocoagulation/char/wetland).

498
499 Differing biodegradability may be assessed by the COD/BOD ratio (Figure 5b), which can be
500 an indicator of organic matter biodegradation (Destro et al., 2020; Lindamulla et al., 2022;
501 Pinedo-Hernández et al., 2024; Mella et al., 2017). A COD/BOD value in the range of 1.5 -
502 2.5 indicates the presence of biodegradable organic pollutants, while a higher value indicates
503 the presence of pollutants that are hardly or not biodegradable and is characteristic for
504 industrial wastewater (Lee&Nikraz, 2014). In the case of the tested effluents, all four samples
505 were characterized by a favourable COD/BOD ratio of approximately 2, which, however,
506 increased significantly between the 14th and 45th day of purification in all tested systems (up
507 to a maximum of 27.6 in the case of CW3) except for CW2, where it remained at 2.

508 3.4 Effluents toxicity evaluation

509 The changes in toxicity of effluents from various treatments, as measured with the
510 Microtox™ assay, are summarised in Table 7.

511

512 Table 7. Changes of toxicity during the various treatment processes – bioremediation, adsorption, and electrocoagulation (average values, n=3).

Experimental set up	Toxicity	Time (days)				
		0	14	30	45	60
CW1 (UCG wastewater)	EC50	0.12	1.05	1.17	104	115
	TU	835	98	85	0.96	0.86
	Toxicity classes	V	IV	IV	II	II
	Toxicity assessment based on EC50	Highly toxic	Toxic	Toxic	Non-toxic	Non-toxic
	Toxicity assessment based on TU	Extremely toxic	Highly toxic	Highly toxic	Slightly toxic	Slightly toxic
CW2 (UCG wastewater after electrocoagulation)	EC50	0.08	2.03	0.67	116	122
	TU	1204	74	65	0.8	0.75
	Toxicity class	V	IV	IV	II	II
	Toxicity assessment based on EC50	Highly toxic	Toxic	Toxic	Non-toxic	Non-toxic
	Toxicity assessment based on TU	Extremely toxic	Highly toxic	Highly toxic	Slightly toxic	Slightly toxic
CW3 (UCG wastewater + adsorbent)	EC50	0.12	0.65	1.84	91.0	118
	TU	835	153	54	1.09	0.84
	Toxicity class	V	V	IV	II	II
	Toxicity assessment based on EC50	Highly toxic	Toxic	Toxic	Non-toxic	Non-toxic
	Toxicity assessment based on TU	Extremely toxic	Highly toxic	Highly toxic	Toxic	Slightly toxic
CW4 (UCG wastewater after electrocoagulation + adsorbent)	EC50	0.08	3.01	2.2	98.0	129
	TU	1204	230	150	2.1	0.70
	Toxicity class	V	V	V	III	II
	Toxicity assessment based on EC50	Highly toxic	Toxic	Toxic	Slightly toxic	Non-toxic
	Toxicity assessment based on TU	Extremely toxic	Highly toxic	Highly toxic	Toxic	Slightly toxic

513 Both, UCG wastewater and UCG wastewater after electrocoagulation had remarkably high
514 toxicity. The toxicity of effluents significantly decreased after 14 days of treatment process in
515 the case of bioremediation treatment (wetland columns CW1 and CW2). The reduction of TU
516 value was around 90% for both treatment systems, and the effluents were classified to IV
517 class of toxicity. In comparison, for the systems combining bioremediation with the use of
518 adsorbent (wetland columns CW3 and CW4) the toxicity of the effluents decreased less
519 remarkably and the effluent maintained the same V toxicity class. In these cases, the observed
520 decrease of leachates toxicity measured by TU values was around 75%. After 30 days of the
521 treatment, the effluents from the columns were toxic, despite a significant decrease in the
522 concentration of the initial compounds in raw post-processing waters (Tables 5 and 6). This is
523 due to the formation of degradation intermediates of BTEX, PAHs, and phenols, most of
524 which are more toxic than the initial substrates. A significant decrease in toxicity was
525 observed after 45 days of treatment in all treatment systems. After this time, the effluents
526 collected from wetland columns CW1 and CW2 belonged to the toxicity class no. II (slightly
527 toxic) according to the classification of Persoone et al. (2003), while the toxicity of the same
528 effluents evaluated based on EC50 parameter were non-toxic. Similar results were obtained
529 after 60 days of the treatment. In just 14 days, the CW1 and CW2 systems achieved a 90
530 percent toxicity reduction, while over a period of 60 days the lowest toxicity value was
531 measured in the system with the addition of adsorbent (CW4). It is also worth emphasizing
532 that after 45 days, despite exceeding some indicators (COD and BOD), the CW1 system did
533 not show any toxicity. Summarizing, only slightly differences were observed between toxicity
534 assessment among four studied treatment systems and minor differences were observed when
535 using the two toxicity classification systems.

536 The assessment of the remediation effects of natural and constructed wetland systems has
537 traditionally been based solely on physicochemical parameters. However, several researchers
538 have stressed the need to include bioassays to better monitor the impact of wetland
539 remediation technologies, incorporating various toxicity tests into their studies (Lutterbeck et
540 al., 2018; Calheiros et al., 2019; Ashraf et al., 2020; Lutterbeck et al., 2020; Celma et al.,
541 2021; Berego et al., 2022). Among these, the Microtox test has been identified as particularly
542 sensitive and effective in evaluating the toxicity of both treated and untreated wastewater
543 samples (Calheiros et al., 2019). In our research, the Microtox test has proven to be a valuable
544 complement to the commonly analysed physicochemical parameters, especially for assessing
545 the progress of the wetland remediation process.

546 4 Conclusions

547 Evaluation of the applicability of the integrated process of four systems combining
548 electrocoagulation, constructed wetlands and adsorption for the effective treatment of UCG
549 wastewater showed that all tested systems were effective in removing contaminants.
550 Verifying the effectiveness of hybrid treatment systems on wastewater with such a complex
551 matrix enable their application to contaminated wastewater from other industrial processes.
552 The conducted research allowed for the formulation of several important conclusions:

- 553 1. Combination of EC and CW proved effective in removing PAHs. CW was found to be
554 more effective for the removal of phenolic compounds and BTEX. Due to the
555 physicochemical properties of the tested UCG wastewater, EC is not a required pre-
556 treatment for the use of CW.
- 557 2. Electrocoagulation is necessary in the case of Fe, B, Co, Mo removal. Regarding the
558 efficiency of both EC and CW for the removal of metals and metalloids, the best effects
559 were observed for Fe, Ni, Sb, As, Cr, Zn, Al, and Ti and the weakest for Mn, B, Co, Cu
560 and Mo.
- 561 3. Longer CW treatment time (45 days vs 14 days) does not entail a positive effect on all
562 tested physicochemical parameters and it may have an adverse effect in the case of COD,
563 TOC, and some metals (Fe, Mn, As, Cr, Zn, Al, Co and Ti). Not only the selection of the
564 appropriate method, but also the optimization of treatment duration seems crucial for the
565 wastewater treatment.
- 566 4. The use of an adsorbent in the form of post-process UCG char does not change the
567 treatment method by constructed wetlands, however, it may reduce removal of some
568 metals (Sb, As, Cr).
- 569 5. For a 14 days treatment, EC-CW system turned out to be the most effective in toxicity
570 reduction. Introducing an adsorbent into the system may improve its efficiency in the
571 long term, as seen in the example of adsorbent-EC-CW system. Effective toxicity
572 reduction from V class to II class after 60 days in comparison with meeting the
573 requirements contained in the BAT document, shows that all tested systems were
574 favorable in terms of UCG wastewater treatment.
- 575 6. No significant difference was observed in terms of testing the toxicity of individual
576 systems. Studies have shown that toxicity assessment should be one of the evaluation
577 criteria for industrial wastewater treatment. This approach is essential for effectively

578 evaluating the performance of wastewater treatment based on natural or constructed
579 wetland systems.

580 Obtained laboratory-scale results can be the basis for designing effective, profitable, and
581 environmentally friendly purification system in a pilotscale.

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